

THE DEVELOPMENT OF PREDICTION EQUATION FOR PIEZOELECTRIC CONSTANTS OF GLASS FIBER EPOXY COMPOSITES

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1 General Introduction

Composite materials were widely used in various applications due to high specific strength, specific modulus and damping characteristic. However, Composite materials need to ensure structural reliability that occur defect in manufacturing and using. Therefore, non-destructive damage monitoring methods for composite materials are very important to enhance structural reliability. The main purpose is the development of prediction equation for piezoelectric constant of glass fiber epoxy composites to develop self sensor type non-destructive damage monitoring system using piezoelectric characteristic of composite materials [1~3].

2 Experiments

2.1 Materials and specimens

Specimens were fabricated using various glass fiber reinforced epoxy polymer as shown in Table 1. Specimens were manufactured by Hand-layup process in the mold, cured in Hot-Press for two hours at 80 ° C under 0.6MPa, and cut 10x10x10 mm size using diamond wheel cutter. The surface was cleaned up by acetone and distilled water, dried in the oven, and applied electrode using conductive silver paste on the surface.

Table 1 Specification of materials

Type	Product No.	Corporation
Plain	G103	Sk Chemical
Satin	G209	"
Unidirection	G220	"
Chopped strand mat	M723-300	Owenscorning
Epoxy	YD-115	Kukdo Chemical

2.2 Apparatus and procedure

Experimental apparatus as shown in the Fig.1 to measure piezoelectric constants of glass fiber reinforced epoxy composites. We applied the 1 Hz sinusoidal compressive loads using universal testing machine (AG-IS, Shimadzu), and then measured electric charge signal of specimen through charge amplifier (Type 2692, Bruel&Kjaer, Denmark) and DAQ (9217, National Instrument Co., USA). The piezoelectric constants were obtained using the linear relationship between Electric Flux Density and Stress.

3 Results and discussions

Experimental results as shown in the Fig.2 (a) depict that the absolute values of piezoelectric constants d_{31} were increased as the fiber orientation changed from 0 to 90 degrees. The predicted values by Eq. (1), which is similar to the transformation matrix in composite mechanics, were well agreed with experimental results.

Fig.1 Experimental setup for measuring piezoelectric properties of glass fiber reinforced epoxy composites.

Fig.2 Piezoelectric constants of glass fiber reinforced epoxy composites compare experiment constants with predicted constants; (a) d_{31} with respect to fiber orientation (b) d_{31} with respect to volume fraction (c) d_{33} with respect to volume fraction.

$$[d^{\theta}] = \begin{bmatrix} \cos^2 \theta \cdot d_{31} + \sin^2 \theta \cdot d_{32} & \cos \theta \sin \theta (d_{32} - d_{31}) \\ \cos \theta \sin \theta (d_{32} - d_{31}) & \sin^2 \theta \cdot d_{31} + \cos^2 \theta \cdot d_{32} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

Experimental results as shown in the Fig.2 (b) and (c) represent that the absolute values of d_{31} and d_{33} were decreased with respect to the fiber volume fraction. Using the rule of mixture and the assumption that the glass fibers have much lower piezoelectric constants than the epoxy, another two prediction equations (Eqs.(2) and (3)) could be derived.

$$d_{31,c} = d_m v_m (pC / N) \quad (2)$$

$$d_{33,c} = d_m v_m (pC / N) \quad (3)$$

Eqs.(2) and (3) also can estimate d_{31} and d_{33} of glass fiber epoxy composites as shown in Fig.2 (b) and (c).

4 Conclusions

In this work, we predicted piezoelectric constants of glass fiber reinforced epoxy composite materials. By comparison between predicted result and experimental results, it showed similar results. So piezoelectric constant of glass fiber reinforced composite materials can be predict using Eqs. (1)~(3).

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References

- [1] H.Y. Hwang "Effect of strain rate on piezoelectric characteristics of unidirectional glass fiber epoxy composites". *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 45, No. 6, pp 613-620, 2011.
- [2] H.Y. Hwang "Electromechanical characteristics of unidirectional glass fiber epoxy composites". *Polymer Composites*, Vol. 32, No. 4, pp 558-564, 2011.
- [3] H.Y. Hwang and D.G. Lee "Prediction of the Crack Length and Crack Growth Rate of Adhesive Joints by Piezoelectric Method". *Journal of Adhesion Science and Technology*, Vol. 19, No. 12, pp 1081-1111, 2005.